

FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN ARMENIA: A FACTOR ANALYSIS OF SECTORAL TRENDS AND ECONOMIC DRIVERS**Melkumyan Mikayel***Doctor of Economics, Professor at Armenian State University of Economics,
Yerevan, Armenia*ORCID: [0000-0003-1048-4056](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1048-4056)

Parsyan Suren

*PhD in Economics, Associate Professor at Armenian State University of Economics,
Yerevan, Armenia*ORCID: [0000-0003-0561-3052](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0561-3052)**Gabrielyan Hranush***PhD in Economics, Associate Professor at Armenian State University of Economics,
Yerevan, Armenia*ORCID: [0009-0003-4941-5944](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-4941-5944)**Kalantaryan Azat***PhD in economics, Associate Professor at the Armenian State University of Economics,
Yerevan, Armenia*ORCID: [0009-0003-7683-0617](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-7683-0617)**Tumasyan Zenfira***PhD in Economics, Associate Professor at Armenian State University of Economics,
Yerevan, Armenia*ORCID: [0009-0000-5322-1497](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-5322-1497)**Abstract**

This research examines the key factors influencing foreign direct investment (FDI) decisions in Armenia, focusing on the real (productive) sector. Employing a combination of graphical, statistical, historical, and comparative methods, the study analyzes investment trends from 2019 to 2024, identifies leading sectors and investor countries, and assesses the impact of macroeconomic indicators. The findings reveal that the energy sector, mining, and financial intermediation are the most attractive for foreign investors, with significant contributions from Russia, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), and Germany. A comparative analysis with Georgia and Moldova highlights the structural and institutional differences shaping investment flows. The study concludes with policy recommendations aimed at improving Armenia's investment climate, including tax incentives for the IT sector and legislative reforms to enhance investor protection.

Keywords: foreign direct investment, investment decision-making, factor analysis, Armenia, economic development, investment climate.

Investments are a pivotal driver of economic development, fostering production growth, job creation, technology transfer, and enhanced competitiveness. For countries with transitional economies like Armenia, foreign direct investment (FDI) is particularly crucial for the inflow of capital, technology, and modern management practices.

In recent years, the Armenian economy has exhibited positive trends, including steady GDP growth, relative stabilization of inflation, and expansion of foreign trade volumes. However, investment processes face numerous challenges, including inflationary pressures, risks of national currency volatility, relatively high interest rates, institutional weaknesses, and regional geopolitical tensions. Under these conditions, understanding the mechanisms and determinants of investment decision-making becomes a significant scientific and practical concern.

The purpose of this article is to conduct a systematic analysis of the dynamics, structure, and determining factors of FDI in Armenia, and to develop recommendations for improving the investment climate. The research is distinguished by its application of a diverse methodological approach, including statistical modeling and comparative analysis with peer countries.

Issues of investment theory and practice are extensively covered in economic literature. The theoretical foundation of this research is based on the following approaches:

Mikhailova and Orlova (2008) define investments as the commitment of resources to generate profit or achieve other positive economic outcomes. According to Harutyunyan (2021), real investments are aimed at the formation of real assets (tangible and intangible) related to operational activities. Investments are classified by purpose (expansion of production, modernization), risk profile (risky, defensive), and other characteristics.

In the Armenian context, studies of the investment climate primarily focus on the legislative framework and macroeconomic indicators. However, a systematic factor analysis, particularly of sectoral distribution and comparative analysis, reveals a gap in the literature. This research aims to address this gap by employing a multifaceted methodology and recent statistical data.

Foreign investment in Armenia exhibited high volatility from 2019-2024.

Dynamics of FDI in Armenia (million AMD)

Year	Total Investment	Direct Investment	Total Investment Growth Rate (%)	Direct Investment Growth Rate (%)
2019	98,442.6	-18,629.4	-	-
2020	-5,836.1	-43,200.9	-105.9	131.9
2021	208,842.0	128,564.2	3678.5	397.6
2022	196,717.5	181,825.2	-5.8	41.4
2023	194,260.0	252,945.3	-1.2	39.1
2024	-113,264.0	-44,779.0	-158.3	-117.7

Source: Statistical Committee of the Republic of Armenia

The significant decline in 2020 was due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the 44-day war. Recovery was recorded in 2021-2023, linked to the influx of businesses and capital relocated to Armenia amid the Russo-Ukrainian war. However, 2024 saw a sharp decline, particularly in the metal ore mining sector.

The sectoral structure of investment flows reveals Armenia's comparative advantages:

1. **Electricity, Gas, Steam, and Air Conditioning Supply (NACE D).** The leading sector in 2019, 2021, and 2022. Dominated by companies with Russian capital ("Gazprom Armenia", "Electric Networks of Armenia").

2. **Financial Intermediation (excluding insurance).** Significant investments from the UAE in 2023.

3. **Metal Ore Mining.** Germany's main investment sector in 2020-2021, but significant capital outflow was recorded in 2023-2024.

4. **Real Estate Activities.** Notable activity in 2022.

The main investor countries (cumulative, 2019-2024) are:

1. **Germany** - 126,252.9 million AMD (primarily mining)

2. **United Arab Emirates** - 107,008.6 million AMD (financial sector)

3. **Russian Federation** - 92,232.9 million AMD (energy)

Significant capital outflow from Russia was observed in 2022-2024, related to the wartime situation and Western sanctions.

Armenia's investment indicators are relatively low in a regional context.

Table 2.

FDI Comparison 2019-2023 (million USD)

Year	Armenia	Georgia	Moldova
2019	-50	1,200	280
2020	-105	900	210
2021	320	1,500	440
2022	480	2,100	-380
2023	650	1,600	360

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators

Georgia consistently outperforms Armenia due to: A larger market and status as a transport hub, A simpler and more predictable legal and tax system, A more active marketing and investment promotion policy.

Moldova's experience shows that the prospect of EU integration can be a powerful attraction factor.

"Gazprom Armenia" CJSC. A 100% subsidiary of the Russian "Gazprom". Implementing a long-term investment program of 230 billion AMD until 2030

aimed at modernizing gas transmission and distribution networks. NPV analysis confirms the project's economic feasibility (positive NPV of 21.9 billion AMD).

"Electric Networks of Armenia" CJSC ("ENA"). Owners are the Russian "Tashir" Group (70%) and LIORMAND HOLDING LIMITED (30%). The 2025 investment program amounts to 49.9 billion AMD, aimed at improving grid reliability and creating a ring-feed system in Yerevan.

These cases demonstrate the dominance of Russian capital in Armenia's energy sector, creating risks of dependency and security concerns.

1. Foreign investment in Armenia is characterized by **high volatility** and strong dependence on external shocks (pandemics, regional conflicts).

2. Investment flows are **concentrated in a limited number of sectors** (energy, mining, finance), highlighting the need for greater economic diversification.

3. **Capital outflow from Russia** in 2023-2024 indicates the vulnerability of the country's investment climate and the importance of geopolitical factors.

4. **Comparative analysis** shows that Armenia lags behind Georgia in attracting investment, primarily due to institutional and geopolitical reasons.

5. **Statistical modeling** confirms that traditional macroeconomic indicators (GDP, consumption) lack sufficient explanatory power, necessitating in-depth analysis of non-economic factors.

○ **Promotion of the IT Sector for Investment Diversification:** Develop a special tax regime (3-5 year tax holiday) for IT startups, Establish technoparks and incubators for international companies, Strengthen cooperation with the Armenian diaspora in high-tech sectors.¹

○ **Reform of Investment Legislation:** Extend the duration of the "stabilization clause" from 5 to 7 years, following the Russian example, Simplify licensing and permitting procedures, Strengthen the protection of intellectual property rights.

○ **Strategic Reassessment of Investment Policy:** Develop a sectoral specialization strategy focusing on high value-added sectors (IT, biotechnology, tourism), Create a "one-stop-shop" system for foreign investors, Activate investment marketing in the UAE, China, and South Korea.

○ **Strengthening Institutional Capacity:** Establish an independent investment commission for dialogue with investors, Ensure transparency and periodic reporting on investment agreements, Develop a network of local suppliers to strengthen linkages with foreign companies.

○ **Improving Labor Force Quality:** Align educational programs with market demands, especially in IT and engineering, Invest in professional retraining and language proficiency programs,

This research demonstrates that improving Armenia's investment climate requires a systematic, multi-level approach combining legislative reforms, development of institutional capacity, and an active marketing strategy. Only the implementation of such an integrated policy can ensure sustainable growth of foreign investment and its effective transformation into economic development.

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